

Project Management In Healthcare Workshop

وزارة الصحة و البيئة

المركز الوطني للتدريب و التنمية البشرية

The National Center for Training and Development

يرحب بكم

An introduction to healthcare improvement projects

Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi

Advisor doctor and expert trainer

Leadership in medicine and healthcare: An accredited training course

Management principles for doctors

Medical leadership

EXPERT TRAINER

Principles of training and development for physicians

Healthcare system in Iraq

Medical and Healthcare Leadership: A training course

Healthcare improvement projects are performed to improve the services in a hospital, a healthcare center, or a healthcare system.

Global healthcare improvement projects are performed to improve health throughout the world.

The need for a healthcare improvement project

A healthcare improvement project is needed when there are indicators of a poor service:

Lack of patients' satisfaction in a primary healthcare center, a hospital, or in the whole healthcare system.

Excessive referral to hospital in a primary care center.

Your healthcare improvement project

**Is there any healthcare improvement project
that you want to perform?**

**What are the indicators of
a poor service that will benefit
from you project.**

**You will have the opportunity
To answer at the end of this presentation.**

Types of healthcare improvement projects

Healthcare management projects are aiming at **organizing the service and it can be performed by heads of departments, and managers of hospitals and healthcare centers.**

Types of healthcare improvement projects

Healthcare leadership projects are aiming at **innovating the service** by introducing a new service such as screening for genetic disease or infectious disorders, and establishing a new specialized consultation clinic for example, a child psychiatry clinic. Healthcare leadership projects can also be initiated or performed by heads of departments, and managers of hospitals and healthcare centers.

Types of healthcare improvement projects

Medical leadership projects are aiming at **improving medical practice** through introducing advances or innovations, and it can be achieved by the highly specialized and expert physicians. For example, changing the practice of closing VSD by stem cells techniques rather than by open heart surgery.

Indicators of a poor service

It was reported to the management of a hospital that many patients at the consultation clinics are spending too much time and effort to complete the investigations at the distant lab and radiology department, and thus reducing **patients satisfaction.**

The appropriate action may include:

A-Asking the doctors not to request lab tests and imaging studies during the same day.

B-Advising the patients to perform the investigations in a private lab and private radiology clinic.

C-A small healthcare management project aiming at organizing the service by withdrawing blood samples by a nurse available at the consultation clinics.

D-A medical leadership project to improve the practice of the doctors at the consultation clinics.

Indicators of a poor service

The management of a healthcare center noticed **excessive referral** of patients with asthmatic attacks to the hospital. The appropriate action may include:

- A-Asking the doctors not to refer patient with asthmatic attack to hospital.
- B-Asking the doctors to prescribe antibiotics for asthmatic patients instead of referring them.
- C-Analyzing the referred cases.

Analysis

A health improvement project begins with **Analysis** to determine what area in the service needs improvement and how improvement can be achieved. For example:

- Too many patients and few healthcare providers.
- Excessive referral from the organization or to the organization.**
- Lack of patient's satisfaction.**
- Lack of investigations.
- Shortage of medication.
- Outdated practices.

Indicators of a poor service

The management of a healthcare center studied excessive referral of patients with asthmatic attack to the hospital, and found that the majority of the referred patients received only Ventolin nebulizer at the hospital, and didn't require hospitalization.

Indicators of a poor service

The appropriate action may include:

A-Asking the doctors to refer all patients with asthmatic attack to hospital to receive Vontolin nebulizer.

B-Small healthcare leadership project aiming at innovating the service through introducing ventolin nebulizer.

C-A medical leadership project to improve the practice of the doctors at the healthcare center.

Indicators of a poor service

The management of a healthcare center investigated excessive referral of patients with asthmatic attack to the hospital, and found that the majority of the referred patients didn't receive adequate medications, and at the hospital they received medications available at the healthcare center. The hospital reported that the center was referring patients with asthmatic attacks that could have been treated satisfactorily on outpatient basis.

The appropriate action may include:

A-Asking the doctors to refer all patients with asthmatic attack to hospital to receive to receive the appropriate treatment.

B-Advising the patients to go to hospital without a referral letter so that the hospital will not report excessive unnecessary referrals.

C-A medical leadership project to improve the practice of the doctors at the healthcare center by conducting a training workshop or organizing a lecture for them.

The **analysis phase** also involve determining the main aims of the project (e.g. reducing the number of referral of patients with asthmatic attack that don't need hospitalization).

Determining the main intervention (e.g. providing a nebulizer in a primary healthcare center).

Analysis

The **analysis phase** also involves determining the aims and main outcome of the project (e.g. enabling a primary healthcare center to treat asthmatic attack that don't need hospitalization).

Determining what resources (Human and material) are required, and their cost.

Indicators of a poor service

The department of pediatrics noted that many of the parents of patients with disabling hereditary disorders had more than one affected children and complained that no one advised them about the possibility of having an other affected child.

The appropriate action may include:

A-Asking the doctors to refer mothers of children with hereditary disorders to a gynecologist for tubal ligation.

B-Asking the doctors to refer fathers of children with hereditary disorders to a urologist for vasectomy.

C-A healthcare leadership project aiming at establishing a genetic counseling clinic at the hospital.

Indicators of a poor service

It was reported to the management of a primary healthcare center that the available antibiotics covered only about 25% of the antibiotics prescribed.

The appropriate action may include:

A-Asking the higher authorities to provide more antibiotics.

B-Asking the patients to get the prescribed antibiotics from a private pharmacy.

C-Analyzing the needed for excessive antibiotics prescription.

Analysis

The management of a healthcare center studied shortage of antibiotics and antibiotic prescription and found that antibiotics were mostly prescribed for self-limited viral infections.

The appropriate action may include:

A-A simple healthcare management intervention with procurement of the necessary antibiotics.

B-Healthcare management intervention with a change in allocation of antibiotics in the total budget.

C-Medical leadership intervention aiming at improving the medical practice of the doctors by conducting a training workshop or symposium about antibiotic abuse and antibiotic resistance.

Analysis

The **analysis phase** also involves determining the tasks, procedures, interventions required to complete the project.

The analysis phase also include SWOT analysis, risk analysis, and analysis of the responses of the stakeholders and their involvement.

Implementation and Monitoring

Implementation of the project with taking the necessary actions to make the necessary change such as the procurement of a nebulizer, holding a training workshops.

Monitoring the outcomes of the project and achievement of objectives, for examples checking the reduction in referrals.

Indicators of a poor service

At the pediatric psychiatry clinic, many parents of patients with mental retardation and autism expressed their **unsatisfaction** as they have already consulted adult psychiatrists who prescribed drugs that made their children sleep such risperidone or prescribed medications that didn't show any effectiveness such as omega-3, folic acid, and vitamins, and now they are being told that there are no effective interventions for their children.

The appropriate action may include:

A-Advising the parents to visit themselves an adult psychiatrist to help them in relieving their tension.

B-Advising the parents to adhere to prayers so that god might intervene.

C-A medical leadership project with introducing an effective evidence-based innovative therapies.

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The National Center for Taining and Development

Amir A Mosawi

**A new therapeutic approach
for pervasive developmental
disorders**

Amir A Mosawi

**A novel therapeutic
approach for idiopathic
mental retardation**

Thank you for joining us today. I hope you are all satisfied for what you came for.

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